

www.arseam.com

INFLUENCE OF Bi³⁺ SUBSTITUTION ON THE STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES Mn-FERRITE

V. D. Murumkar

Department of Physics, Vivekanand Arts, Sardar Dalipsingh Commerce and Science College, Aurangabad, Maharashtra State, India

Abstract

Bi³⁺ substituted MnFe₂O₄ ferrite with a chemical formula Bi_xMnFe_{2-x}O₄ were synthesized by sol-gel auto combustion method. As prepared samples were sintered at 800 °C for 4 h. In order to calculate the structural properties such as lattice constant, X-ray density, bulk density, surface area, crystallite size, hopping lengths and allied parameters X-ray diffraction were carried out. X-ray diffraction pattern confirmed the formation of single phase cubic spinel structure upon Bi³⁺ substitution. It has been observed that lattice constant and bulk density increased with Bi³⁺ substitution. Hopping lengths decreased whereas all the allied parameters increased with Bi³⁺ substitution.

1. Introduction

Recently, extreme zests have been broadcast into restraining the shape of nano materials and also into understanding the correlations between material properties and its shape. The shape of nano materials can be as vital as the size in determining the uniqueness and novelty of material properties. Moreover, a large part of the societal impact by nano materials surely will be realized in a variety of devices consisting of nano material components. Manganese ferrites belong to a family of soft ferrite materials characterized by high magnetic permeability and low losses. Furthermore, it is also ascribed that Mn ferrites are of inverse spinel structure because 80% of Mn ions occupy tetrahedral site (A-site), which is surrounded by four O²⁻ ions, and the left 20% of Mn ions occupy octahedral site (B-site), which is surrounded by six O²⁻ ions. The cation distribution for Mn ferrites can be represented by (Mn²⁺_{0.8}Fe_{0.2}³⁺)^A [Mn³⁺_{0.2}Fe²⁺_{0.2}Fe³⁺_{1.6}]^B O₄ [1,2]. These materials are predominantly consumed in numerous applications such as microwave devices, computer memory chips, magnetic recording media, radio frequency coil fabrication, transformer cores, rod antennas and many branches of telecommunication and electronic

engineering [3-6]. Sol-gel auto-combustion method is simple, economical and which basically keeps the characteristics of the powder as much under controls possible (purity, chemical homogeneity, shape and size of particles). The combustion method presents some advantages over other methods: the reagents are simple compounds and do not require any special equipment, the doping can be easily introduced, and the agglomeration of powders remains limited. Moreover, it has proven to be quite promising to obtain nano-structured ferrite powders. Small amount of substituent ions can be used to modify microstructure properties of ferrites. Therefore, in the present work Bi^{3+} were used as a substituent ion for Fe^{3+} in MnFe_2O_4 ferrite to investigate the structural changes.

2. Experimental procedure

Samples of Bi substituted MnFe_2O_4 ferrite were synthesized by sol-gel auto-combustion method using the nitrates of Mn and Fe ions. Reaction procedure was carried out in air atmosphere without the protection of inert gases. The molar ratio of metal nitrates to citric acid was taken as 1:3. The decomposition reaction would not stop before the whole citrate complex was consumed. The auto-ignition was completed within a minute, yielding the brown-colored ashes termed as a precursor. The as-prepared powders of all the samples were sintered at 600 °C for 4 hr. The X-ray powder diffraction patterns were recorded by using $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation on Philips X-ray diffractometer (Model PW3710) at room temperature.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 X-ray Diffraction

Figure 1 shows the XRD patterns of the prepared ferrite powders for $\text{Bi}_x\text{MnFe}_{2-x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0.0, 0.05, 0.1$ and 0.15). The background noise and broadness of the peaks appeared in Fig. 1 are characteristic of particles with nanometer dimensions. This happens because in the nanosized particles there are insufficient diffraction centers that cause the line broadening. The matching of the standard d values with the observed planes in the diffraction patterns confirms the formation of a cubic spinel structure. The main reflections from planes (220), (311), (222), (400), (422), (511) and (440) characterizing spinel ferrites are clearly observed without any trace of detectable

impurity. The XRD of the prepared sample (Bi_xMnFe_{2-x}O₄) seems to be different from one another, mainly due to (i) the concentration of Bi³⁺ cations, (ii) the difference in the crystal size of the obtained powder, and (iii) relative change in lattice constant.

Fig. 1: X-ray diffraction patterns of Bi_xMnFe_{2-x}O₄ sintered for x = 0.0 and x = 0.15.

The lattice parameters were calculated from the XRD patterns data and are presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Variation of lattice constant with Bi³⁺ substitution.

The lattice constant is influenced by the cationic stoichiometry. The lattice parameter values which were calculated using Bragg's Law showed a significant change with the substitution of Bi^{3+} . It is observed that lattice constant increased with the Bi^{3+} substitution. This may be due to the larger ionic radii (1.03 Å) of Bi^{3+} as compared to Fe^{3+} (0.67 Å) ions. The average crystallite size was calculated from the (311) diffraction peak of the XRD profiles using the well-known Debye Scherer equation [7]; $t = \frac{0.9\lambda}{B \cos\theta}$, where λ is the wavelength, B is full width at half maximum intensity in radian, θ is Bragg angle. The crystallite size laid in the range of 29-35 nm with increase in Bi^{3+} concentration.

Fig. 3: Variation of crystallite size and specific surface area with Bi^{3+} substitution.

Specific surface area (S) is also calculated from the size of the crystallite and are presented in Fig. 3. The X-ray density (ρ_x) of all the samples of the series was obtained by the following relation.

$$d_x = \frac{ZM}{NV} \quad (1)$$

where Z is the number of molecules per unit cell, M is molecular weight of sample, N is the Avogadro's number and V is volume of unit cell. Figure 4 shows the variation of X-ray density with Bi³⁺ substitution. It can be noted from Fig. 4 that the X-ray density increases with decrease in Bi³⁺ substitution. This increased in X-ray density is related to the increase in molecular weight of the sample and lattice constant. The bulk density (d_B) measured using the formula;

$$d_B = \frac{m}{\pi r^2 h} \quad (2)$$

where m is mass, r is the radius and h is the height of the pellet. Figure 4 shows that bulk density is also increased upon Bi³⁺ substitution. This behaviour is related to the lower melting point of Bi³⁺ ions.

Fig. 4: Variation of X-ray and bulk densities with Bi³⁺ substitution.

Using the values of lattice constant ‘a’, the distance between magnetic ions (hopping lengths) available in tetrahedral A-site and octahedral B-site i.e. ‘ L_A ’ and ‘ L_B ’ respectively was calculated by using the relations,

$$L_A = a \sqrt{3} / 4 \quad (3)$$

$$L_B = a \sqrt{2} / 4 \quad (4)$$

Fig. 5 shows the relation between the hopping lengths in octahedral (A) and tetrahedral [B] sites as a function of Bi^{3+} substitution. The distance between the magnetic ions decreased with the increase in Bi substitution. This may be attributed to the fact that the lattice constant increases with Bi substitution.

Fig. 5: Variation of hopping lengths L_A and L_B with Bi^{3+} substitution.

The bond length of tetrahedral A-site and octahedral B-site i.e. shortest distance between site cations and oxygen ions along with tetrahedral edge, shared and unshared octahedral edge, are calculated using the

formulae given below [8,9] by inserting the values of lattice constant and oxygen position parameter in to these formulas.

$$d_{AX} = a\sqrt{3}\left(u - \frac{1}{4}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$d_{BX} = a\left[3u^2 - \left(\frac{11}{4}\right)u + \frac{43}{64}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (6)$$

$$d_{AE} = a\sqrt{2}\left(2u - \frac{1}{2}\right) \quad (7)$$

$$d_{BE\text{shaired}} = a\sqrt{2}(1 - 2u) \quad (8)$$

$$d_{BE\text{unshaired}} = a\left(4u^2 - 3u + \frac{11}{16}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (9)$$

The variation of these structurally important parameters are shown in the Fig. 6 and 6. It can be observed from Fig. 6 that the tetrahedral bond (d_{AX}), octahedral bond (d_{BX}), tetra edge (d_{AXE}) and octahedral edge (d_{BXE}) in both the ferrite systems are increased with Bi³⁺ substitution.

Fig. 6: Allied parameters with Bi³⁺ substitution

While comparing the results of both the systems it is observed that all the parameters shows increasing trend with the increasing Bi^{3+} substitution. The variation in all the allied parameters are associated with the variation of lattice constant.

4. Conclusions

Bi^{3+} substituted MnFe_2O_4 ferrite were successfully synthesized by the sol-gel auto-combustion technique. Structural analysis with XRD reveals that the system confirms the formation of single phase cubic spinel structure. Lattice constant increased with Bi^{3+} substitution due to the larger ionic radii of Bi^{3+} ions as compare to Fe^{3+} ions. X-ray and bulk density increased with the Bi^{3+} substitution. Nanostructure formation is confirmed as the crystallite size is ranges from 29 to 35 nm. Hopping lengths and allied parameters shows the variation based on the lattice constant.

References

- [1] R. H. Kadam, A. R. Biradar, M. L. Mane, Sagar E. Shirsath, J. Appl. Phys. 112 (2012) 043902.
- [2] Sagar E. Shirsath, B. G. Toksha, R. H. Kadam, S. M. Patange, D. R. Mane, Ganesh S. Jangam, Ali Ghasemi, J. Phys. Chem. Solids 71 (2010) 1669.
- [3] Q.M. Wei, Jian-biao Li, Yong-jun Chen, Yong-sheng Han, Mater. Charact.47 (2001) 247.
- [4] J.A.T. Taylor, S.T. Reczek, A. Rosen, Soft ferrite processing, Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull. 74 (4) (1995) 91–94.
- [5] M. Rozman, M. Drogenik, J. Am. Ceram. Soc. 81 (7) (1998) 1757–1764.
- [6] S.H. Chen, S.C. Chang, L.N. Lin, J. Magn. Magn. Mater. 209 (2000) 193–196.
- [7] B. D. Cullity, “Elements of X-ray diffraction”, (Addison-Wesley Publ. Comp. Inc., Reading, Massachusetts, U.S.A.) (1956), 99.
- [8] Santosh S Jadhav, Sagar E. Shirsath, B. G. Toksha, S. M. Patange, S. J. Shukla, K. M. Jadhav, Inter. J. Mod. Phys. B 23 (30) (2009) 5629-5638.
- [9] J. Smit and H.P.J. Wijn, “Ferrite”, Philips, Technical Library Holland (1959) 240.